

Technical note describing the assimilation impact

Deliverable 3, European Space Agency Project -Performance Evaluation of Arctic Weather Satellite Data (No. 4000136511/21/NL/IA)

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1. Introduction

This document is a short summary note describing the assimilation impact of the project enhancements made with respect to use heritage sensors and more extensively described in project deliverable D2 [1]. The quality evaluation and assimilation impact of the AWS instrument will be addressed in coming deliverables D9 ('Quantification of AWS data quality and timeliness and preliminary Harmonie-Arome impact assessment') and D10, on 'Impact assessment of AWS to regional NWP and NWC'. Some of the developments presented here for heritage sensors were immediately found beneficial and have already reached operations, while others require some more developments and refinements before they can be applied.

2. Assimilation and forecast impact summary

Here we focus on summarising the assimilation and forecast impact studies carried out to evaluate key developments in the HARMONIE-AROME forecasting system carried out within the project. These developments were about 1) the introduction of the dynamical emissivity approach, under either specular or Lambertian reflection assumptions, to make better use of surface sensitive MW channels and 2) the development and the application of a footprint operator to handle scale differences between MW radiance observations and model equivalent. In addition we describe the main results obtained from impact studies based on AWS project developments towards use of satellite radiances both from clear and cloudy/rainy regions (all-sky). The status of the assimilation and forecast impact reported in section 4.2 of D2 is summarised in Table 2.1 below.

Table 2.1: Assimilation and forecast impact of enhanced handling of heritage MW sensor radiances

Enhancement	Assimilation and forecast impact	Remark
<p>Dynamical emissivity approach for low-peaking MW channels around 50 GHz and 183 GHz with special handling of 183 GHz over ice-covered surfaces. See section 3.1 in D2 for a detailed description.</p>	<p>Positive impact demonstrated on forecast skill. Demonstration both in AWS project impact studies and pre-operational runs.</p>	<p>Enhancements activated as default in reference AWS HARMONIE-AROME model branch and operations.</p>
<p>Footprint operator to handle scale differences between MW satellite observation and forecast model. See section 3.2 for detailed description.</p>	<p>The overall impact of the radiance footprint operator is neutral to positive and significant positive impact was obtained in particular for short term (up to 12 h) temperature forecasts initialised from 06 UTC analyses. Impact larger on 3D-Var than on 4D-Var, probably due to coarser incremental 4D-Var assimilation.</p>	<p>Enhancements are not yet considered mature enough with respect to flexibility and computational cost to be activated by default in the reference AWS HARMONIE-AROME model branch nor operations.</p>
<p>Introduction of Lambertian surface reflection assumption to replace specular assumption. See section 3.1 in D2 for a detailed description.</p>	<p>Mixed results on analysis and forecasts. Looks promising with introduction of Lambertian reflection assumption for 50 GHz surface sensitive channels over snow covered surface.</p>	<p>Revised reflection assumption not ready to enter reference code. Additional extended experiments for different surfaces are needed and code generalisations to allow combined Lambertian/Specular reflection assumption.</p>
<p>Evaluation and refinement of all-sky functionality for MW observations from the MHS instrument. See section 3.3 in D2 for a detailed description.</p>	<p>First cycled data assimilation and forecast experiments in AWS project showing proper functionality. Extended parallel experiments showing</p>	<p>All-sky approach not applicable in AWS HARMONIE-AROME branch. Ported to common</p>

	overall neutral forecast impact and encouraging results for a case study [2].	HARMONIE-AROME code and planned for pre-operational studies during 2025.
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3. Conclusions

We conclude that the developments carried out within the AWS project and focusing on an improved use of MW radiances in Nordic conditions have greatly benefited the HARMONIE-AROME system and also future use of AWS instrument radiances. Some of the research results have already reached operational use while others require some more refinements before being considered suitable for operations.

4. References

[1] Lindskog, M. *et al.* 2024. Technical note describing the updates of the HARMONIE-AROME system. Deliverable 2. European Space Agency Project -Performance Evaluation of Arctic Weather Satellite Data. No. 4000136511/21/NL/IA. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.10878879>

[2] Guedj, S., Baordo, F., Azad, R. and Mile. M. 2024 . Preliminary results on all-sky MHS data assimilation in the AROME-ARCTIC NWP system. http://www.accord-nwp.org/IMG/pdf/preliminary_results_on_all-sky_mhs_data_assimilation_in_the_arome-arctic_nwp_system.pdf